

The Content of the Discipline of Pedagogical Conflictology and its Importance in the Educational Process

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Abstract: This article, the content of pedagogical conflictology, provides information on the study of the essence of conflicts, the causes of their occurrence, the dynamics of development and ways to resolve them.

Keywords: pedagogical conflict, educational environment, interpersonal relations, communication, mediation, mediation, approach, mechanism.

Today, due to various social, economic and cultural factors, the number of conflicts between people is increasing. These conflicts are also manifested in educational institutions. Therefore, teachers and educators must have the skills to properly manage and resolve conflicts.

The new edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” requires ensuring mutual respect and cooperation between the parties participating in the educational process. The development of the discipline of conflictology serves to fulfill these requirements. At the same time, the professional development and psychological preparation of teachers are identified as the main factors for improving the education system.

The strategy “Improving the Spirituality of New Uzbekistan” for 2022-2026 also provides for strengthening approaches aimed at humanism, a culture of dialogue and conflict prevention in the education system. It provides for the creation of a healthy environment in educational institutions and the introduction of mechanisms aimed at conflict management.

In general, pedagogical conflictology is relevant and important for harmonizing relations between teachers and students, ensuring stability in the educational environment, and effectively organizing the educational process. The content of the discipline of pedagogical conflictology serves the sustainable development of society, the effectiveness of the educational process, and the improvement of interpersonal relations. The resolutions and laws adopted in our country to increase the importance of this discipline are aimed at ensuring social stability in the education system. Therefore, pedagogical conflictology is an important factor not only in the educational process, but also in general social development.

The content of pedagogical conflictology is to study the essence of conflicts, the causes of their emergence, the dynamics of development, and ways to resolve them. This discipline forms theoretical and practical knowledge on the analysis, management, and prevention of conflicts that arise, in particular, in the education system. The essence of the discipline of pedagogical conflictology is to study conflicts on a scientific basis, identify their causes, analyze development processes, and develop ways to effectively manage them. This science

studies the theoretical and practical foundations of resolving conflicts in society and between people. The essence of conflictology is to ensure stability through the analysis and management of interpersonal, intergroup, and systemic conflicts.

The main aspects of the essence of conflictology are that it studies conflict as an integral part of social relations. It substantiates that contradictions are a natural process that occurs in all spheres of life. It identifies the root causes of conflict (lack of resources, clash of views, incorrect communication). It analyzes the stages of conflict development and develops strategies for their resolution. The main goal of conflictology is to ensure peace and stability in society by resolving conflicts constructively. It develops and applies conflict management tools. It is aimed at developing a culture of dialogue, mediation and compromise in personal and intergroup relations. Through this process, it increases mutual understanding and cooperation between people. Pedagogical conflictology is related to social sciences (psychology, sociology, law) and embodies the knowledge gained from them. It develops technologies and methods used in resolving conflicts. It identifies the causes of conflicts and finds ways to eliminate them, and develops methods for constructive management. Improving communication between individuals and groups is about creating a stable and healthy social environment.

It is about creating a healthy socio-psychological environment in the educational environment, preventing conflicts and forming skills for their constructive resolution. This discipline plays an important role not only in improving the relationship between teachers and students, but also in increasing the effectiveness of education. It allows you to timely identify and prevent various conflicts that arise in the educational process. It creates a stable and peaceful environment in educational institutions, which has a positive effect on the quality of education.

Studying the discipline of pedagogical conflictology allows future teachers to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in conflict management, learn to constructively manage interpersonal relationships. The skills of stress management and making the right decisions in problem situations are developed. At the same time, students learn conflict culture, develop communication culture, cooperation and compromise skills, and develop teamwork skills. By improving relationships between teachers and students, the activity and motivation of participants in the educational process increases. It serves to reduce negative emotions arising from conflicts and create an environment of constructive communication.

By managing conflicts, it increases the respect of participants in the educational process for each other. Factors that reduce the effectiveness of education are eliminated and a favorable environment is created for teachers and students by improving psychological services in educational institutions, and stress arising from conflicts and emotional health are supported.

Conflictological skills are formed through special trainings for teachers and students. Along with the use of mediation techniques in resolving conflicts between students, practical exercises are held aimed at teamwork and resolving contradictions. Pedagogical conflictology plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, creating a healthy educational environment, and harmonizing relations between educational participants. Through this discipline, the education system is focused not only on imparting knowledge, but also on developing personal and social skills. This, in turn, serves to increase the quality of education.

The discipline of pedagogical conflictology provides important theoretical and practical foundations for managing the educational process and improving the quality of education. By resolving conflicts, trusting relationships are formed between teachers and students in the educational process. By preventing and resolving conflicts, a positive atmosphere is created in the educational process. This, in turn, increases the effectiveness of education and

increases students' interest in learning. The importance of the discipline of pedagogical conflictology in the educational process is seen in improving relations between teachers and students, preventing conflicts, and improving the quality of education. This discipline serves to create a stable and healthy environment in the education system, as well as effectively managing the pedagogical process.

Pedagogical conflictology not only provides theoretical knowledge, but also provides teachers and other participants in the educational process with practical skills. At the same time, as an integral part of the educational process, it makes a significant contribution to the personal and social development of students and the professional skills of teachers. Teaching effective conflict management mechanisms through this discipline improves the overall quality of the education system.

Conflict management is important in creating an effective pedagogical process and social environment. Conflict resolution mechanisms are implemented through the following approaches:

1. Preventive approach

To prevent conflict from occurring:

- Ensuring open communication between students and the team.
- Creating a positive psychological environment.
- Developing communication skills to build relationships on a healthy basis.
- Identifying and eliminating problems at an early stage.

2. Constructive approach

If a conflict has already arisen, to end it with a positive outcome:

- Seeking compromise in resolving the conflict.
- Taking into account the interests of both parties.
- Discussing the conflict on the basis of mutual respect.

3. Mediation approach (mediation)

Using the help of a third party (mediator) in resolving the conflict:

- The mediator hears the interests of both parties and helps to make a fair decision.
- Organizes effective communication between the participants.

4. Emotional management techniques

It is important to control emotions during the conflict process:

- Use breathing exercises, stress reduction techniques.
- Express negative emotions through positive communication.

Seek to understand the thoughts and feelings of the participants. Provide clear and logical arguments to resolve the conflict. Instead of blaming "you", express your feelings and thoughts in the "I" format (for example, "I am offended by this situation"). The conflict should be resolved with an analytical approach, not an emotional one.

Effective conflict management mechanisms help to ensure a healthy and stable environment in the educational process. Conflicts can be resolved constructively through the use of

prevention, constructive communication, mediation and practical methods. This not only eliminates conflicts, but also serves to improve the quality of education and build trusting relationships.

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